

THE THEORY OF EVERYTHING

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ABSTRACT

Light is shown to have a gas and a liquid phase. Its gas phase is what we know as 'light' and its liquid phase is dark and invisible to us and creates gravity. This dark liquid light moves constantly throughout galaxies, stars and planets and carries a dark EMF. Our stars are vast energy engines creating both hot and cold energy – heat and momentum – described brilliantly by the First Law of Thermodynamics back in 1850. Light has two EMF fields, one light and one dark, one expanding one contracting. These polarized EMF fields connect energetically to baryonic matter through polar covalent molecules such as water to transfer both expansion and contraction to all matter. Gravity is thus a pushing force powered by hydrogen in the sun and carried by dark liquid light throughout 4D spacetime bounded by the curvature described by Einstein. The warm EMF boson is the expanding wave photon and the cold EMF gravity

boson is none other than the contracting particle photon. Or entire universe is floating on a puddle of dark liquid light which has superfluid qualities. Dark liquid light constitutes 'dark matter' and the expensive search for it may now end.

Here are my ideas presenting a solution to the Einstein/Quantum dialectic and the wave/particle paradox describing exactly what causes gravity, what constitutes dark matter and possibly dark energy as well, what the quantum boson of gravity really is and just for kicks, what causes stellar core rotation.

Enough 'real scientific work' has been expended on the unsuccessful search for dark matter. All that remains is human ingenuity, imagination and common sense.

For the record, I am not a physicist and hold only a culinary diploma. To reach this understanding of gravity I have employed nothing more than common sense logic and a spooky jump into the unknown. I cannot be shot for this as Quantum Mechanics already has one toe in the mystical and with photon entanglement possibly a whole foot as well.

We can pick it up where Einstein left off with the alleged wave/particle duality of light. It is somewhat stupefying to me why Einstein himself or any other intelligent thinker in

the century since the great man did not arrive at the same conclusion as I have. I understand why Science eschews the 'spooky' or the 'mystical' but one can genuinely argue that using pedantic scientific methods have only got humanity so far especially with regards to light and gravity.

We know that light can be a wave or a particle however since the photon and even the electron are so tiny by our scale of measurement that we can never see the little fellas directly we must look elsewhere. People will kill to assert that the photon is completely 'massless'. However, we can clearly see the same duality in larger objects in the observable universe and a comparison with light is illuminating and enlightening.

We need look no further than our miracle wonder worker, water. Who does not love a glowing noctilucent cloud shimmering up there with the aurora? A wave pattern is clearly visible as the cloud warms expands and rises up rippling gently floating away while still maintaining its internal integrity as a gigantic water vapor molecule. And we may at our leisure observe the raindrops falling on my hot tin roof or indeed which keep falling on my head. Little liquid water particles falling down down down ratatatatat.

So, a wave function rises up and a particle function falls down. Furthermore, a wave function represents the gas phase of a substance and a particle, the liquid phase.

May we apply the same model to light? Does light rise as an expanding wave in its gas phase and fall as a contracting particle in its liquid phase? We certainly may. They might be

different substances and a question exists whether light even is a substance of mass yet their similar behavior is compelling. In fact, we can see the wave/particle in birds as well especially in predators like falcons and eagles. In the eternal words of Tom Petty RIP: "I'm learning to fly but I ain't got wings. Coming down is the hardest thing."

Water, birds, mosquitoes and even light.

It is surprising that I cannot find this question anywhere but in my own head. It amazes me how people have simply followed Einstein even when he leads you nowhere but into the broom closet!

We know from photosynthesis that plants have a light phase followed by a dark phase which does not reverse or cancel the light but rather finish and complete the cycle. Not only is darkness inherent to the cycle but that darkness is an active element in its own right.

This is where I make the leap into the unknown with nothing but my logic and intuition to guide me. Dark matter has never been found to date using light because maybe that is the nature of things and they do not engage or interfere with one another directly. The dark absorbs energy and cannot reflect light.

I am considering the real possibility that visual light is not where the story begins and that stars do not create light any more than your stove makes the soup being heated up in the pot. And more succinctly, that creeping pyroclastic invisible liquid light is to blame for what we perceive as gravity. That a real pushing force exists throughout time and

space which pushes all atomic baryonic matter along and arranges it all according to weight and density. Simply put, what we are all looking for is the dark, invisible liquid phase of sunlight. And although light and baryonic matter do not cohabit sexually, they do tantrically with energy constantly passing back and forth between these two substances.

A few observations and question. If liquid light can move the densest and heaviest objects in the universe, this would imply that dark liquid light is the heaviest densest substance of all while still remaining invisible and 'massless' to us! At the same time, if light in its gas phase can simply fly out of the core of stars, this implies that visual light is the lightest least dense stuff around. Clearly not bonding physically with atomic matter like electrons do, how then could this substance manage to push and provide momentum to mass at all? If it is true that dark liquid light is pushed into the core of stars to be boiled and converted to its gas phase, why is light not destroyed in the vast heat and pressure involved?

This is where our lack of vision and incorrect labelling become an issue. We call light 'light' because that is what we see even though this only represents its gas phase while its liquid phase is anything but 'light' being both heavy and dark! However, since 'light' is its name, I shall refer to 'bright gas light' and 'dark liquid light'.

We call baryonic matter 'atomic' because we can perceive and see these tiny building blocks yet light is also 'atomic' in the sense that it too is made of bits although far too small for us to see or measure. Light is a complex 'molecule' of

this magic fairy dust and is polar like our water molecule and can change shape like our water molecule. But light is also made from much sterner and denser stuff – exotic metal alloys – indicating it is much older and has finally reached 0 entropy after 100 billion years or more. Substance like this while still observing the rules of density and the Laws of Thermodynamics, exhibits behavior all of its own. Stuff this dense, this energized and this small is nothing less than a time traveller from the distant future. Here is where ‘relativity’ is vital: light is just doing its thing, taking the hund for a walk around the lake, chatting to neighbor Frank over the garden fence; to us, it’s magical, mystical, mind-bending all at once.

Regarding baryonic matter, it’s another story entirely. We have a trillion different names for it ranging from protium to oganesson when, actually, all is one specific substance in a constant state of phase change. (Think only of the Parable of the Mustard Seed.) We can view atomic matter as beginning in its lightest least dense gas phase with hydrogen and then growing constantly heavier denser and changing into its solid phase with the most compact of metals. Atomic matter is one specific substance growing heavier and fatter all the time.

The easiest explanation is that light was not part of our Big Bang which was merely a local excrescence on the surface of our huge spherical blob of dark solid light – a horizontal blip at best. A floating warm puddle on a gigantic cold ocean holding itself together yet slowly spreading and expanding

out. Which would also explain, incidentally, why the universe is flat. Not like a pancake but like a thinning puddle floating and spreading in all directions on the surface of a humungous dense solid superfluid sphere in God's back pocket.

What exists, in essence, is two minster substance locked in a supernal cosmic dance where light helps atomic matter to change from a gas to a liquid to a solid and atomic matter helps light change from a solid to a liquid to a gas. Initially solid light and gas baryons were thrown together. Light existed before, during and long after the Big Bang. A useful analogy is growing a mustard tree in a fertile substrate. Small seeds and massive trees! Think of hydrogen atoms as the seeds and mature galaxies as the trees, their branches dripping with billions of shining fruit-stars. And think of solid light as a fertile substrate for our nascent universe.

The magic that we call life occurs at the nexus point where both atomic matter and light meet at the crossover between liquid and gas phases. Although moving in different directions, at this perfect nexus is where it all happens.

Solid light is at 0K and 0 entropy. Dense heavy inert, it appears as a type 2 superconducting superfluid which everyone is looking for, the Bose-Einstein Condensate and the source of entangled photons. According to the Meissner effect, such a substance repels magnetic flux and this is what we find in the Emf fields of light. I say two Emf fields because light carries two, one hot one cold, one light one

dark, one energy giving and one energy sucking. It is through the magic of magnetism that these polarized force fields can engage with baryonic matter at all.

The best place to look for dark liquid light is to observe what it does to water. These two substances have a unique relationship in our world because light and hydrogen have a unique relationship that powers the universe and holds it all together. Throughout the entire universe, water follows light. It is more probably more correct to say that light creates water and that the entire universe is filled with water. By implication we could probably also conclude that water borne life is ubiquitous everywhere. The whole universe is a conspiracy between hydrogen and light..

Why is water such a wonder? It is the prime Polar Covalent Molecule we have. It mediates many important functions like ozone, ammonia, melanin in our skin, iron magnetite in the crust and life itself. All these polar molecules interact with the polarized magnetic Emf force field of sunshine and darkness. A cloud is one big dipole moment which shifts constantly and aligns itself with the polarized rising heat. The result is untold numbers of electric circuits closing between light and water and the transfer of heat to the covalent electron sharing molecules. Brilliant!

We need to start now crawling through stars like our sun. Again, we are in massive error about how we view these giant energy engines and what happens within them.

Applying the First Law of Thermodynamics to the concept of an Electro-Magnetic force field, we must allow for the

possibility that an Emf can deliver both heat and cold momentum as well. Basic logic really.

Jean's Instability tries to explain stars but doesn't get very far. It turns out that the beautiful First Law of Thermodynamics and not the Theory of General Relativity properly explains stars and gravity. Einstein had enough in front of him to crack the walnut but missed it. He had both the laws of Thermodynamics and the duality of light although, to be fair, he might have lacked a toe in the mystical unseen 'spooky' world where the Hand of God is not Maradona RIP playing dice with the universe.

A good place to kick off is with our Observer friends discovering a glowing hydrogen wall at either edge of the solar system. In reality, a huge hydrogen bubble around the whole solar system and around galaxies, stars, planets and moons. Based on a fractal pattern, each one is a unique gravity field influenced by the others. On earth, we can identify three different fields, all doing different things to the world and us.

Einstein was correct in identifying the 'curvature of 4D spacetime' in respect to gravity and the hydrogen bubble is where it begins. Packed strictly in a tight density regime, these objects are like cosmic Matryoshka dolls with their concentric bubble-layers of increasing density from the lightest hydrogen gas to the heaviest densest solids. Observing Pascal's Law, momentum applied to one will be carried through all layers. Called Hydrostatic Equilibrium, a

star stabilizes with something pushing in and the hot core radiating out.

In mature stars, the pulsating core sends heat out, expanding photons flying out in expanding waves, carrying their heat energy to all mass they encounter, ending in the glowing hydrogen bubble 14 billion km away.

Hydrogen and their covalent bonds are special because of their electron-sharing properties. And because the tiniest protium atom is also the smallest most atavistic of polar dipole moments. These amazing little energy seeds grow into mature galaxies and also power up the stars, their hot inner nuclear cores and their cold outer momentum generators. Our bubble must resemble the massive Atlantic swell in the icy blackness of outer space fed by the constant stream of hot waves. Every point on the circumference rises and falls, up and down, non-stop up and down, generating massive cold force vectors down into the sphere along every radius geodesic aimed directly at one point, the inner core. In the final act of the cold cycle, these momentum vectors ed up once again in the core causing its constant rotation. Gravity is to blame for stellar corer rotation as well.

The first explicit statement of the first law of thermodynamics, by Herr Clausius 1850, referred to cyclic thermodynamic processes.

“In all cases in which work is produced by the agency of heat, a quantity of heat is consumed which is proportional to the work done; and conversely, by the expenditure of an

equal quantity of work an equal quantity of heat is produced.”

The entire galaxy bubble is rooted and immersed within dark liquid light which enters everywhere and is directed towards the core resulting in what we experience as gravity.

Dark liquid light is moved through entire galaxies, star and planet systems, by the cold power generated by hydrogen on its way to be converted into light its gas phase and while it does this, it shlepps all baryon matter reluctantly along for the ride.

How is cold energy – cold electricity – transferred to liquid light and how does it in turn transfer it back to atomic matter? Why, by the power of magnetism and polarized force fields interacting with polar covalent molecules ad vice versa. The hot Emf carried by the expanding wave photon gives out energy freely but what it gives with one hand it takes with the other. Like a vampire in the night, the cold Emf sucks out energy from the very air as it passes through.

Here on earth, the constant flow of dark liquid light into the core carrying a dark Emf field creates what we perceive as constant gravity on us. Explained by Pascal’s Law, momentum is carried through each density layer and is conserved. Magnetism is only needed at a very short distance to align the Emf with the respective polar covalent molecules upon which is applied cold pushing force which is then transmitted through the atoms and the entire system.

The flow of dark liquid light into the earth 24/7 creates cold gravity. The flow of dark light into the sun during our night enhances the contracting force by ruthlessly stealing electrons away from polar molecules causing them to contract atomically for example turning water vapor back into its liquid state. At night, we experience a 'double' gravitational effect contracting us, making us cold and also squeezing us together. Liquid light flow into the moon expands water on the surface of earth with its resultant effects. A complete gravitational diagram must take all effects into account. Although all part of the bigger picture each smaller object and its own field behaves in its unique way. Dark liquid light certainly slows down as it enters each successive system.

Gravity on earth is caused by the constant flow of dark liquid light and contracting photon particles through our atmospheres to our core. Not as hot as a star, our core is responsible for geothermal activity but not our daily burst of visual light. Our day is dominated by light emanating from the sun expanding and warming the entire solar system. At night, this changes into a cold Emf field sucking up energy back. These result in the dramatic increase and decrease of mass in its changing of phases. The moon's gravity field is smaller affecting our moods, the ocean swell – no surprise there – and the weather. Dark light moves nowhere near the Speed of C and slows down further as it enters each smaller system hence gravity on the moon is less than on earth.

As dark liquid light is contracted and forced and squeezed and heated up on route to the stellar core, it is not condensed but rather broken up into 'molecules' to be heated into flowing gas bubbles of expanding visual light.

Gas light and liquid light do not interfere or interact at all which is why liquid light remains forever dark. Like I say, you can't use a noctilucent cloud to locate a single raindrop. It is the same phenomenon as quantum tunnelling.

It is worth pointing out from a purely historical point of view that it appears quite convincingly in some early pagan sun-worshipping cultures, they knew clearly about the two faces of light. Examples will be quoted at the end of this paper.

Water is also the key to locating dark liquid light. Water shape shifts around the VERY SHAPE of photons whether expanding in waves or contracting in particles. The very best place to see the shape of a photon is in water. Using magnetism, water morphs into the exact shape of the Emf in order to maximize 'surface area' and charge transfer. There are 1.5 sextillion water molecules in a rain drop so even a lowly 'massless' particle is a contracting 'molecule' made of many bits of magic fairy dust. So please stop saying the contracting photon particle is massless! There's the guilty party, right there!

The most dramatic example of an observable contracting photon is a lightning bolt which is also poorly understood. As heat rises and expands in waves, its negative charge is on top and a cloud's positive dipole moment is below. The Emf field shoots electrons upwards into the bottom of the cloud.

If the Emf dramatically switches, all the charge below the cloud suddenly finds itself on the negative moment facing down. Now, the Emf literally sucks energy away from the cloud and takes this build-up of electric charge back. Instead of expanding up, the lightning bolt which is one gigantic contracting photon now points directly towards the core and kaplooy, down she goes apparently into the earth but really absorbed by the contracting falling liquid dark Emf force field deep within the earth.

The strongest evidence I can find to the existence of two phases of light, bright and dark, is in our own eyeballs.

The eye absorbs light through two very different channels. The iris with cones, white with color patterns extremely reminiscent of a wave from the spectrum of sunlight, open wide expansively in the eye, is clearly designed for warm expanding bright light waves. And the pupil? Contracting to absorb different inflows, it is dark (DARK!!!) with its black rods, small central pipe-shaped like normal liquid pipes (did I mention it is black?) what for if not for dark liquid contracting dark light?

Through our eyes, light enters the brain directly. In day we stand vertical with our brains adopting a lighter density with visual light. At night we lie horizontal with even body density. During REM, our brains are as active as in the day during our deepest sleep. No wonder Einstein did not see or think of dark liquid light. We see dark light most clearly during deepest sleep or during dreams of falling. Jung had no real idea why we dream of falling. Neither did Einstein.

The existence of dark liquid superfluid light certainly makes the idea of entangled photons easier to comprehend. It completes the picture of what is moving through time and space dragging baryonic matter along with it.

Say hello to our little photon friends, expanding or contracting, flying or sailing along, smiling or grimacing. They been marching a long time and a long way.

The 'hidden light' is the favorite topic of the mystical Kabbalah.

The small book Habahir predates the Zohar and together, they constitute the medieval Kabbalah. This is the very first paragraph of the book:

This Biblical verse (Job 37.21) says "And now people do not see the light which is bright in the heavens" and these verses say (Psalms 18.12) "He makes darkness His secret place" and (Psalms 97.2) "Cloud and mist surround Him" – a contradiction! A third verse comes to resolve this problem (Psalms 139.12) "Even darkness will not be dark to You and night will shine like day. Darkness and light are the same.)"

The Kabbalah raises immediately the duality of light problem in a spiritual context! Job declares that even in his time – estimated some 3,000 years ago – people had already stopped looking directly into the sun as a daily religious practice. And today, one can safely say that speaking quite literally, people universally do not see or look at the light anymore. Spiritual myopia has been a human existential problem for millennia. It

continues to this day and affects incongruously the science realm as much as anywhere else.

The Talmud in Hagiga 12a asks:

“If the sun and the moon were created only on the Fourth Day of Creation, what then is the light created on the First Day? Rebbi Elazar taught that the light of the First Day was a unique and special light. With it, a person could see from one side of the world to the other. When God saw the evil generations of the Flood and the Tower of Babylon and their wicked ways, He stood up and hid this light away as it states (Job 38.15) ‘And from the wicked the light is withheld’. For whom did God hide this light? For the righteous of the Future World as it states (Genesis 1.4) ‘And God saw the light that it was good’ and ‘good’ refers only to the righteous as it states (Isaiah 3.10) ‘Say of the righteous it is good’. Now when God saw the light He had hidden away for the righteous, He became happy as it states (Proverbs 13.9) ‘The light of the righteous gladdens’.”

Says the Zohar Hadash on page 12c concerning the Final Redemption:

“Even at the time of the Creation of the world, was this great secret hinted at among the hidden things. ‘And God said let there be light and there was light’. This means ‘let it be a secret’ for ‘raz’ meaning secret and ‘ohr’ meaning light have the same Gematria value of 207.

The New Testament is full of references to light. John 1:5 “The light shines in the darkness and darkness has not overcome it.”

THE LIGHT SHINES IN THE DARKNESS

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